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1 МАХСУС СОН

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СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

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ON THE ISSUE OF HEARING SCREENING AMONG PREMATURE NEWBORNS <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7824625>**ABSTRACT**

This article is about an audiological screening of premature newborns, and hearing impairment during primary screening, where is noted in 30.3% of cases, which exceeds the general population figures. In order to increase the effectiveness of neonatal hearing screening programs, it is necessary to expand the range of methods used and, at a minimum, supplement it with an ABR test in order to reduce undiagnosed rehabilitation losses and reduce the number of cases of loss of observation, which, of course, will require long-term economic support.

Keywords: premature newborns, hearing impairment, hearing loss, audiological screening, evoked otoacoustic emission delay, ABR-test.

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**К ВОПРОСУ О СКРИНИНГЕ СЛУХА СРЕДИ НЕДОНОШЕННЫХ
НОВОРОЖДЕННЫХ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

При аудиологическом скрининге недоношенных новорожденных нарушения слуха при первичном скрининге отмечается в 30,3% случаях, что превышает общепопуляционные показатели. С целью повышения эффективности программ неонатального скрининга слуха необходимо расширить спектр применяемых методов и, как минимум, дополнить ее АБР-тестом чтобы снизить не диагностируемые реабилитационные потери и уменьшить число случаев потери наблюдения, что, конечно, потребует долгосрочную экономическую поддержку.

Ключевые слова: недоношенные новорожденные, нарушения слуха, тугоухость, аудиологический скрининг, задержка вызванной отоакустической эмиссии, АБР-тест.

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ERTA TUG'G'ALAR O'RTASIDA ESHITISHI SKRININI SAVOLGA

ANNOTATSIYA

Erta tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarni audiologik skrining paytida birlamchi skrining paytida eshitish qobiliyatining buzilishi 30,3% hollarda qayd etilgan, bu umumiy aholi sonidan oshib ketadi. Neonatal eshitish skrining dasturlari samaradorligini oshirish uchun diagnostika qilinmagan reabilitatsiya yo'qotishlarini kamaytirish va eshitish qobiliyatini yo'qotish holatlarini kamaytirish uchun qo'llaniladigan usullarni kengaytirish va hech bo'lmaganda uni ABR testi bilan to'ldirish kerak. kuzatish, bu, albatta, uzoq muddatli iqtisodiy yordamni talab qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: erta tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar, eshitish qobiliyatining buzilishi, eshitish qobiliyatini yo'qotish, audiologik skrining, otoakustik emissiyaning kechikishi, ABR-testi.

Introduction. The introduction of neonatal hearing screening programs into neonatological practice in many countries of the world, including the Republic of Uzbekistan, allows early diagnosis of hearing loss and deafness in newborns.

Neonatal hearing impairments are reported in 2-3% of premature newborns and 0.1-0.2% in full-term newborns since prematurity is a significant risk factor for hearing loss [13].

Congenital hearing impairments, in particular genetically determined ones, are recognized as the most common genetic pathology in the UK (1.33 per 1000 newborns) and the USA (1.86 per 1000) [6].

But it should be noted that hearing loss at the age of 2–3 years is already 2.7 per 1000, and at 4–5 years, it is found in 3.5 per 1000 children [11].

It must be understood that the perception of sounds, in particular within the “speech frequencies” (500-4000 Hz), i.e., hearing is an essential condition for the development of normal speech in a child, as part of language development, even some hearing loss in a child, often not diagnosed in infancy and early childhood, negatively affects the formation of language skills and the usefulness of speech, behavioral and emotional development of the child [10].

The earliest detection of deafness provides the child with the opportunity for early cochlear implantation and the early onset of the perception of sounds that ensure the formation of his speech [9].

In economically developed countries, the standard for diagnosing deafness is 3-6 months from birth, gradually reducing this interval to 2-3 months of life [4].

However, there are practically no studies on the early diagnosis of hearing loss and rehabilitation of hearing in children in the first 6 months of life, although the negative impact of II and III degrees of hearing loss on speech is undoubted.

There is no doubt that it is necessary to conduct not only a study of the presence of hearing or its absence but also to determine the degree of hearing loss in the examined children since this is vital in terms of the quality of life of a child and an adult in the future, will provide adequate electroacoustic correction of hearing impairment and, if its early implementation will allow the child to develop speech skills in parallel with healthy peers and without the involvement of a teacher of people who are deaf or hard of hearing for his education, which will favorably affect his socialization and cognitive development, and will also be more cost-effective.

The purpose of the study: is to analyze the effectiveness of the current neonatal hearing screening program and evaluate the possibilities for its improvement among preterm infants.

Material and methods: Hearing studies were carried out at the Regional Perinatal Center of the Khorezm region of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 2021 to 2022. During the study period, 12891 children were born in the center, among them 4417 premature newborns with a gestational age of 22 to 37 weeks, which amounted to 34.3%.

To assess hearing in neonatological screening, portable devices for delayed evoked otoacoustic emission (DIOAE) were used, and the MADSEN Accuscreen device (GN Otometrics, Denmark) was used [16].

ZVOAE devices can register 8 or more reliable peaks with an artifact value of up to 20%. However, it gives an answer only in the “passed” and “failed” parameters, i.e. there is a rumor and it is not, which does not meet modern requirements. TEOAE determines the response of the outer hair cells of the organ of Corti to auditory signals [9], has high sensitivity (80-96.5%) and specificity (90.6-92.85%) [3, 10].

In parallel with TAAE, in cases of average risk of hearing impairment in children at 4-6 weeks, we conducted a test for an automatic auditory response of the brainstem (automated brainstem response – ABR) with the use of small ear tips or small headphones, 3 small pads in the ears of the examined children, the device sends signals in the form of clicks, the response and interpretation of the reaction to which displays the level of the auditory nerve [16].

The first TEOAE test was performed on day 2-3 of life. The study was repeated in the first month of life for newborns who did not pass the first test. The studied children with negative and positive results of the TEOAE test were further examined by the ABR test, MSCT and MRI of the skull were performed with an emphasis on the labyrinth of the pyramids of the temporal bones to exclude organic pathology.

It should be noted that our study did not include newborns with any genetic anomaly and syndromes, as well as children with diagnosed malformations, as well as children from closely related brothers in order to exclude genetic genesis.

Results and discussion: Among the examined premature newborns, 67.9% (2999 out of 4417 births) had otoacoustic emission during primary screening, and in 30.3% (1338 out of 4417) cases the test results corresponded to “test failed”.

Of all 1338 preterm infants with no otoacoustic emission on an ABR test 4-6 weeks after birth, 52.4% (701 newborns) had an ABR hearing impairment, with 12.12% failing both TEOAE tests. Consequently, out of 1338 premature newborns, the TEOAE reveals 30.3% of hearing impairments, while the ABR test - is 52.4%, and one of the advantages of this method is the determination of the degree of hearing loss of the subjects.

It should also be remembered that the TEOAE test has many false positive results, reaching 16.7% [14], and making a false, albeit preliminary, diagnosis causes concern for parents [8].

The addition of a second TEOAE test before discharge in infants who fail the first test reduces the rate of false diagnosis to 1.9-3.3% [2].

Another significant disadvantage of using only TEOAE is the many newborns who fall out of the follow-up audiological follow-up they need [14].

Parental attitude also has a significant impact on hearing loss [12]. French researchers give data on the loss of 48.3% of violations, and German colleagues talk about 31.3% losses [15].

Misunderstanding of parents and some fear of hearing loss and deafness of the child determine the formation of psychosocial reasons for skipping studies and consultations, ignoring the recommendations of specialists, which leads to the lack of timely rehabilitation of the hearing of newborns [12], worsen their subsequent quality of life and socialization.

The use of modern computer systems based on ID and guaranteeing the safety and confidentiality of private data and information is aimed at a nice explanatory work of a doctor with parents in terms of the importance and need for further examinations and consultations aimed at the earliest possible rehabilitation of hearing impairment in children [5].

In our study, we stated that only in close and adequate cooperation between neonatologists and an otorhinolaryngologist- audiologist in terms of building complete trust between parents and staff it is possible to minimize the proportion of the undiagnosed hearing loss. In contrast, the lack of

explanatory work with parents is almost guaranteed to lead to the impossibility of early hearing rehabilitation.

In the future, fruitful and adequate interaction between an otorhinolaryngologist- audiologist and a pediatrician will significantly increase the readiness of parents for hearing rehabilitation, relative to monoactivity an audiologist, since the necessary correction of hearing loss with hearing aids or cochlear implants (according to the degree of hearing loss) [7] is designed to provide children with the opportunity for adequate socialization and quality of life, which should be the aim of the screening, diagnosis and rehabilitation program of hearing, which implies enormous economic costs, time and professional resources to help children [1].

In conclusion, we concluded that in order to increase the effectiveness of neonatal hearing screening programs, it is necessary to expand the range of methods used and, at a minimum, supplement it with an ABR test in order to reduce undiagnosed rehabilitation losses and reduce the number of cases of loss of observation, which, of course, will require long-term economic support. Collaboration between an otorhinolaryngologist- audiologist and a pediatrician, a joint patient-centered approach, and an increase in the number of trained personnel, equipment and financial support will allow specialists to carry out an adequate early diagnosis of hearing loss in newborns due to an adequate and competent implementation of the dogmas of the hearing screening program, literacy and continuity of infant hearing research.

We have established that audiological screening should be performed on all newborns, especially among premature newborns. At the same time, primary screening should be carried out using TEOAE while supplemented for 4-6 weeks with the ABR test.

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ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

1 МАХСУС СОН

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